

QuADTool: Analyzing PAC-Quantitative Attack-Defense Trees

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Abstract QuADTool is a tool to model and analyze (quantitative) attack-defense trees, a widespread formalism for security assessment.

Since the support for the analysis of these models is scattered over various tools and differs in the model features allowed, we provide a unifying GUI framework interfacing with the other tools as well as our own analysis algorithms. Most interestingly, we provide a “PAC-input” quantitative analysis. While standard quantitative analyses may distinguish likely from unlikely vulnerabilities, they rely on *precise* quantitative inputs (probabilities, timing, or costs of attacks), which are rarely available. In contrast, previous experience may provide enough data for a *probably approximately correct* estimate of the real quantity.

The imprecision and uncertainty of the input quantities are thus bounded and propagated during our PAC-input quantitative analysis, bounding the imprecision and uncertainty of the final result of the analysis. Moreover, the tool provides support for accurate modelling of the PAC inputs as well as the corresponding analysis, incurring virtually no overhead. Finally, the tool comes also with a benchmark suite, on which we demonstrate its effectivity.

1 Introduction

Attack trees, e.g. [32, 57], and their extensions are a widespread formalism for security assessment in industry and research. Applications of attack trees range from analyzing attacks on smart grids [4], ATMs [20], optical power meters [19], SCADA control systems [11, 41, 55, 38, 15] or software supply chains [45] to intelligent autonomous vehicles and vehicular networks [27, 30, 49], secure deployment of HTTPS [54] or cybersecurity awareness trainings for election officials [53]. Moreover, attack trees are particularly useful for meta-modeling threats, combining several risk analyses together, e.g. in telemedicine [29, 48], impersonation attacks in e-learning [50] or IoT systems [34]. Besides these individual usages, attack trees are generally recommended as means to identify the point of the weakest resistance according to the *OWASP CISO AppSec Guide*³, or to retrospectively understand attacks (through so-called red teams) by NATOs *Improving Common Security Risk Analysis* report [44].

Since, in practice, there are not enough resources to fix every single vulnerability found in security assessment, the need to rank their importance arises. *Quantitative*

³ https://www.owasp.org/index.php/CISO_AppSec_Guide:_Criteria_for_Managing_Application_Security_Risks

analysis of attack trees can utilize quantitative information such as probabilities, costs, and timing to compute how likely certain vulnerabilities are, how much cost/damage attacks may cause, or how long attacks might take. Consequently, it can distinguish unrealistically costly or improbable attacks from those that need to be fixed. While there is a recent body of theoretical work in this direction, e.g. [35, 26, 3, 46, 36, 33, 18], there are two main hindrances to practical use. Firstly, it is the very *limited tool support* for convenient quantitative modelling and analysis. Secondly, it is the *uncertainty and imprecision of the quantitative input* information, arising in this domain even more than elsewhere. Indeed, apart from standard questions like *What is the actual failure rate of the security camera?*, we may need to ask *What is the probability to guess a password using a database of most common passwords and one year CPU time?* or *How much faster and cheaper is a particular attack going to be next year based on the data of past years?*

In this paper, we address both issues: we provide a convenient *tool*, which also features quantitative analysis capable of rigorously reflecting the *uncertainty and imprecision of the quantitative inputs*. To this end, we formalize such models as *PAC-quantitative trees*, show how to practically obtain them using our tool, and provide an algorithm for their analysis.

PAC-quantitative attack-defense trees. All the previously cited quantitative analyses assume that the quantities (transition probabilities, costs, delays) are given as exact numbers, allowing analyses to output exact numbers, too. However, in reality, we often lack perfect data and can only collect measurements of costs and probabilities. This allows us to derive estimates of the true value, possibly together with confidence intervals bounding the uncertainty of these estimates. Hence, we assume the input quantities are *probably approximately correct (PAC)*, i.e., with a given probability in a given interval around the estimate. We demonstrate how easily such trees can be obtained directly within our tool. To that end, we consider not only independent samples of the unknown quantity but also the more practical case of temporal data (e.g. past years' information), relying on time-series analysis. We then extend the traditional bottom-up analyses to bound the final PAC uncertainty resulting from the PAC uncertainty of the input quantities. Interestingly, our extended analysis comes at virtually no additional computational cost compared to the standard analysis. As a consequence, our approach allows

practitioners to stick to their current analysis and, with almost no additional effort, learn about the quality and reliability of its results.

Tool. We provide *QuADTool*, a tool for the whole modeling-analysis workflow. The tool can import trees in the DOT format and XML format of *ADTool* [21], and we provide a benchmark collection in these formats. The GUI allows for convenient creating, editing, and combining trees, as well as generating PAC-quantities directly from the data. Further, the tool translates the trees to formats of model checkers UPPAAL [5], PRISM [37], PRISM-games [13], MODEST [25], and STORM [17] (via JANI [8] export of MODEST). Consequently, the GUI effectively interfaces with other available analyses (such as [21, 51]) as well as to our new PAC-input analysis. Besides, in order to help non-experts to successfully construct meaningful models, we provide detailed automatically generated feedback on compliance with the assumptions of each of the offered analyses.

To summarize, our contribution is a tool addressing practical needs in attack-tree modeling and analysis:

- GUI editing of attack trees and a rich range of their extensions, interfacing analyzers together with helpful feedback, a benchmark collection;
- estimating quantities in the models from data, and extending analyses to rigorously reflect the uncertainty in the resulting PAC models (at almost no additional cost).

Organization. The paper is organized as follows. After exemplifying the framework of attack trees in Section 2, we describe the tool functionality in Section 3 and our PAC-input analysis in Section 4. Section 5 evaluates our contributions experimentally and Section 6 concludes. An extended version of this paper including the formal definitions for Section 2 and Section 4 and all proofs can be found at [10.5281/zenodo.4095068](https://zenodo.org/record/4095068). Both the tool and the benchmarks are available at <https://www7.in.tum.de/~kraemerj/upload/index.php>.

Related work. Besides two industrial tools dedicated to attack tree analysis⁴, which neither support more complex attack-defense tree structures such as [26], nor export to standard model checking tools, there are three dedicated (and up-to-date) *quantitative* attack-defense tree analysis tools:

- ADTool [21] supports attack-defense trees with the operators AND, OR and SAND and attack-defense trees with operators AND and OR. Quantitative analysis is performed using the standard bottom-up traversal. In contrast to our tool, neither PAC-input analysis is possible (it cannot be added as a ‘custom’ domain since multi-parameter attack trees are not supported), nor richer constructs available (e.g. defense, further operators).
- ATTop [51] is a software bridging tool, which provides various horizontal and vertical model transformations to the ADTool 2.0 input format or to the model checker UPPAAL, however not to PRISM or MODEST. Clearly, PAC models and PAC analysis are not supported.
- RisQFLan⁵ allows specifying attack-defense trees with quantitative constraints using a dedicated probabilistic language. Statistical model checking and exact analysis using STORM and PRISM are supported. In contrast to our tool, PAC-inputs and continuous-time are not supported and exports to STORM and PRISM rely on discrete-time Markov chains rather than games or stochastic timed automata.

Uncertainty in Attack Tree Analysis. Surprisingly, the uncertainty of the input quantities in attack trees has not gained too much attention yet [10, 42, 46]. For similar formalisms, most importantly fault trees [56], uncertainty is limited to fuzzy approaches [52]. The first approach to account for inconsistency and gaps in historical data and experts’ estimates on attack trees is presented in [9]. The main limitation of that approach is that it is not possible to reflect the data accuracy, which is exactly what we address in this paper.

⁴ see <http://www.amenaza.com> and <http://www.isograph.com/software/>

⁵ <https://github.com/RisQFLan/RisQFLan/wiki>

2 Attack-Defense Trees

In this section, we briefly recall the notion of *attack-defense trees* (ADT), e.g. [26]. Attack-defense trees are labeled trees, where the root represents the overall goal to attack a system. This goal can be recursively refined into smaller sub-goals, giving rise to descendant nodes, until no further refinement is possible. Nodes with children are labeled with operators binding the roles of the children. The leaves, which cannot be refined any further, represent *basic events* (denoted BE), unique observable happenings in the real world. They are partitioned into *basic attack steps* and *basic defense steps*.

Figure 1: This attack tree represents how to gain access to an exemplary computer system. We use this toy model as a running example. In Section 5 we evaluate our tool on more complex attack-defense trees.

Example 1. In Figure 1, we present a small attack tree, which represents an attacker who wants to maliciously gain access to a computer system. The goal node (with blue border) represents the overall attack goal. All leaves of the tree are either basic attack steps (colored red) or basic defense steps (colored green).

The semantics of the trees is as follows. The players may *attempt* their basic events *successfully* or *unsuccessfully* (or not at all). Then, the operators define how the successful attempt of a basic event is propagated (bottom-up) through the tree. For instance, the operators **AND** and **OR** propagate successful attempts like their logic equivalents: **AND** propagates successful attempts if all its children are successfully attempted (independently of the order), **OR** propagates a successful attempt if at least one child is successfully attempted.

Example 2 (Continued Example 1). The goal is refined into different subtrees using the operator **OR**, i.e. only one of subtrees need to be successfully attempted for the overall attack to be successful. The overall attack is successful if, for instance, the victim forgets to lock itself out of the target computer (event (2)). Two further subtrees are refined using the operator **AND** (events (6) and (17)). To successfully attempt the subtree rooted in event (6), the attacker needs to get the PIN (event (4))

and to steal the victim’s phone (event (5)) to use the smart login function of the target computer.

To model more complex attack-defense scenarios, a richer set of operators

$$O = \{\text{AND, OR, NOT, SAND, SOR, TR, RE, COST}\}$$

are necessary: **NOT** is successfully attempted if its child is unsuccessfully attempted (and vice versa).⁶ **SAND** and **SOR** pose temporal (but not causal) restrictions on the order in which its children are attempted. Specifically, for **SAND** to be successfully attempted, all its children need to be attempted successfully in order (from left to right). Further, if the child of **TR** is successfully attempted, several basic events are activated (*triggered*) for attempting (they cannot be attempted earlier than this). We say that these basic events are *triggered*. Finally, **RE** is successfully attempted if its child is attempted successfully. As a side effect, events reset can be attempted again, i.e. we allow one event to be tried several times.

3 Functionality

QuADTool allows handling attack-defense trees both in a graphical user interface and using direct command-line access. Here we demonstrate the usage of the tool focusing on the graphical user interface.

Figure 2: Workflow with QuADTool

3.1 Modeling

The workflow using QuADTool (see Figure 2) starts with model construction. For convenient modelling, QuADTool supports two different input formats besides its graphical user interface:

⁶ In contrast to [31], we use the operator **NOT** to include defense mechanisms rather than player swapping. Hence, we strictly separate events controlled by the defender from countermeasures since actions of the defender can also be profitable for the attacker and actions of the attacker can also prevent an attack.

- The **dot**-format as described in the Graphviz-Tool [22]. It provides a human-readable and lightweight language for complex graph structures. Vertices and edges can be specified in a single line. We recommend this format as it supports storing all additional parameters like PAC-parameters and nice formatting.
- The **XML**-format used in **ADTool** [21]. All vertices of the attack-defense tree are converted into XML nodes, each having other nodes in their hierarchy. Due to the strict tree structure of XML, only tree-like attack-defense trees with a single root node can be stored. It is not possible to directly store PAC-parameters within the model.

The *GUI*, see Figure 1, offers drag-and-drop manipulation of trees, creating new ones from scratch or by import. One can also easily create combined models by importing several trees and connecting their vertices in the usual way. Our editor is lightweight enough to handle models with over a thousand states.

There exist various approaches to attack-defense tree analysis supporting different features (see [57] for a survey on quantitative attack-defense tree analysis). Hence, QuADTool comes with an integrated *feedback system* to support the user in finding potential errors or incompatibilities before exporting. Furthermore, it gives advice on which export formats may be beneficial for the particular model.

To support the standardization and benchmark collection among attack-tree researchers and practitioners, we maintain an attack-tree *database* at <https://www7.in.tum.de/~kraemerj/upload/index.php>. Our editor includes an automated interface for uploading models to our database.

3.2 Obtaining PAC-Quantities for Attack-Defense Trees

In this section, we illustrate that in many application scenarios for attack trees, it is practically feasible to obtain realistic input quantities, for instance, by means of a time-series analysis. Consequently, our PAC assumption is not only less restrictive than the standard assumption of exact quantities (and thus applicable in more situations), but already very realistic for various practical applications. Unfortunately, most real safety- and security-relevant datasets might reveal high-confidential business secrets and, thus, are not publicly available. Therefore, we illustrate the usage in a more general example. We use the crime data-set from UK [43] to generate the probability for the event *steal phone* Figure 1 to take place.

The data contains the amount of individuals being impacted by police reported phone theft and an estimate of the total individual phone owners in the area. Having this data we can calculate the probability for a single phone user to be victim of phone theft. To now derive PAC-parameters, the simplest way is to calculate a Gaussian estimate with confidence intervals. Another common option is to build an AutoRegressive-Moving Average (ARIMA) model [6, 14, 58, 12, 40, 28] and predict the values for the next period of time. Both options are integrated and directly accessible in QuADTool.

While the Gaussian estimate is best for independent identically distributed (i.i.d.) samples, in our example, it is not possible to see the samples as independent as they were drawn from the same population and may influence each other e.g. a year with high crime rates may lead to more police activity and therefore influence the following year.

Therefore, a ARIMA model may better represent the situation, as the data points are of equal time periods. To allow for such analysis QuADTool includes a library [47] for automated time-series analysis. The tool checks the possible parameter permutations for an ARIMA model and chooses the version with the lowest Akaike information criterion (AIC). This parameter was proposed to allow relative comparability between multiple models in terms of the prediction error [1].

Using the data from 2009 to 2018, this setup returns the estimate of 0.72% with an uncertainty of 0.19% given a δ of 5%. This estimate has the true value for the next period, the second half of 2018 until the first half of 2019, 0.69% in its range. We ignored the latest data including the first half of 2020 on purpose due to the corona pandemic.

Please note that we do not aim to create the best possible time-series model for a given data-set using our tool as this would still require a more detailed analysis. However, we want to allow inexperienced users to easily get a fairly good prediction.

3.3 Export

Once the model is constructed, it can be exported to five file-formats: XML, DOT, PRISM, MODEST, UPPAAL. For PRISM, we use the semantics in terms of stochastic turn-based games given in [18] and for MODEST and UPPAAL the semantics in terms of stochastic timed automata given in [26]. (To use STORM, we suggest to use the export to MODEST first and then, use their export to the JANI-format.) Now we describe the interfaces to other tools and their use in more detail.

Connection to ADTool and ATTop. Since these attack-tree tools have a restricted set of features, some trees cannot be exported as they are. For instance, due to the **XML**-structure of ADTool and ATTop, whenever a model has multiple root nodes our export omits all except one tree-structure. Furthermore, the ADTool only supports the operators **OR**, **AND**, **SAND** and no timed events (with clocks or distributions). In the current development version (2.2.2), **SAND** trees do not have a domain for minimum costs and success probability; fortunately, we were able to add custom domains to fill this gap. An advantage of this format is the strict separation between attacker and defender processes (if it is not a **SAND**-tree): ADTool can assign subtrees to either attacker or defender, which improves human readability.

Timed Analysis. Analysis involving time can be either done within QuADTool or outsourced to MODEST or UPPAAL.

The translation to **MODEST** is based on actions for each three-valued logic state, i.e. each basic event can either be undecided, successfully or unsuccessfully attempted. A basic event signals all its successors being successfully attempted by the action **ttBEPlayerx** (where x is the id of the event). This approach in turn makes possible to model systems with multiple root nodes and complex operators. Additionally, timed basic events can be sampled from a given distribution. Since MODEST can be converted to JANI and back by the MODEST toolset [24], all model checkers supporting JANI become also available.

Another model checker supported by QuADTool is **UPPAAL**. It has an easy-to-use GUI for modeling and simulation [16]. Due to a different synchronization mechanism in UPPAAL, we save the value of each event as integers rather than

as states of the automaton. All potential goal vertices are connected to an automaton called *Won*, which then determines whether the attack is successful or failed. Thus, we can, for instance, calculate the overall success or fail probability of the attack-defense tree. These two properties are automatically created on export. With UPPAAL, we were able to handle large models in a reasonable amount of time, as presented below. However, this approach does not support games.

Game Analysis. Lastly, QuADTool can export also to the **PRISM** format, not supporting time, but supporting games. In this framework, all basic events have the same chance to be executed at a given (discrete) point in time, which impacts the evaluation of sequential operators.

3.4 Analyses

Similar to the ADTool, QuADTool supports direct analyses on the tree for exact minimal and maximal attack costs, exact minimal and maximal attack delays and exact success probabilities. Additionally, we support PAC-input analyses for each of these domains, which we discuss in the next section.

4 PAC-Quantitative ADT: Fighting the Uncertainty

A standard way to reason about costs, probabilities and time within attack-defense trees is to equip basic events with quantitative information and use bottom-up traversal algorithms to derive the final value for the root. In this section, we show how to adapt the bottom-up analyses to bound the uncertainty coming from imprecise quantities of basic events. Here we focus on *probabilities*; however, QuADTool supports bounding uncertainty for *costs* and *delays*, too.

4.1 Quantitative ADT and PAC-Quantitative ADT

Quantitative ADT

Given a type T of the quantitative information, the quantitative ADT is an ADT equipped with a *quantitative valuation of basic events* $\text{val}_{\text{BE}} : \text{BE} \rightarrow T$. The definition is generic to cater for various settings: While real numbers may represent cost, acyclic phase-type distributions may, for instance, represent the likelihood of a successful attack over time.

Example 3. For success probabilities, we simply take $T = [0, 1]$.

PAC-Quantities

In most real-world examples, the quantitative information attached to basic events is rarely known precisely, but rather comes with some uncertainty. We call quantitative information to be *probably approximately correct (PAC)*, if there is an *imprecision bound* ϵ and an *uncertainty probability* δ , such that the distance between the true value and the given estimate is less than ϵ with probability at least $1 - \delta$. Formally:

Definition 1 (PAC). Let \mathbb{T} be a set equipped with a metric d . We say that a \mathbb{T} -valued random variable X is (ϵ, δ) -PAC with respect to the true value v if the probability⁷ of $X \in \{t \mid d(t, v) \leq \epsilon\}$ is (at least) $1 - \delta$.

Exact values can be considered $(0, 0)$ -PAC.

Example 4. For success probabilities, the metric is the standard Euclidean distance (absolute value of their difference).

PAC-Quantitative ADT

Given a type \mathbb{T} of the quantitative information, the PAC-quantitative ADT is a quantitative ADT equipped additionally with *PAC-parameters* $\epsilon_{be} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $\delta_{be} \in [0, 1]$ for each basic event $be \in \text{BE}$.

4.2 Quantitative Bottom-Up Analyses

Before giving the generic algorithm for the bottom-up propagation of quantitative values [39, 31], we summarize the following building blocks it relies on:

- The algorithm is parametric in the *domain* \mathbb{T} of the quantitative information.
- All basic events of an ADT need to be given values from \mathbb{T} in order to start the bottom-up propagation. We thus assume a *basic-event valuation* function $\text{val}_{\text{BE}} : \text{BE} \rightarrow \mathbb{T}$ to be given as the input to the procedure.
- The algorithm is also parametric in the *interpretation* l , which maps the ADT-operators to operations over \mathbb{T} , so that we know how to propagate the values. It must satisfy the following conditions:
 - $l(\text{op}) \in \mathbb{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{T}$ for $\text{op} \in \{\text{NOT}, \text{TR}, \text{AND}, \text{OR}, \text{SAND}, \text{SOR}, \text{RE}\}$, where n is the arity of op
 - $l(\text{be}) \in \mathbb{T}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{T}$ for triggerable basic events $be \in \text{BE}$ allows for reflecting the value of the triggering event into the final value of the triggerable basic event.

Example 5 (Probabilistic ADT).

We have already seen that the domain for probabilities is $[0, 1]$. Here we instantiate the interpretation for probabilities. For simplicity, consider only the operators **AND**, **OR**, **TR** and **NOT**. We define a probabilistic interpretation l (with $\mathbb{T} = [0, 1]$) as follows:

- $l(v)(x_1, x_2) = x_1 \cdot x_2$, if v is a triggerable basic event or $t(v) = \text{AND}$
- $l(v)(x_1, x_2) = x_1 + x_2 - x_1 \cdot x_2$ for $t(v) = \text{OR}$
- $l(\text{NOT})(x) = 1 - x$

⁷ The probability space is typically given by the method used to learn the estimate X from data sampled from a distribution parametrized by v . For instance, for a v -biased coin with $v = 0.49$ and 20 samples (coin tosses), the standard statistics methods yield a probability space with highest density of X in 0.49 and inducing the respective confidence intervals for X depending on the outcome of the experiment.

Bottom-Up Traversal Analysis

Let ADT be an attack-defense tree with set V of nodes, g its root, T a non-empty domain, I an interpretation, and val_{BE} a basic-events valuation. Then its bottom-up traversal semantics $\text{val} : V \rightarrow T$ for ADT is defined recursively as

$$\text{val}(v) = \begin{cases} \text{val}_{\text{BE}}(v) & \text{if } v \in \text{BE}, \text{ and } v \text{ is non-triggerable.} \\ f(\text{val}_{\text{BE}}(v), \text{val}(u)) & \text{if } v \in \text{BE}, v \text{ is triggerable, } I(v) = f, \\ & \text{and } u \text{ triggers } v. \\ f(\text{val}(in_1) \dots \text{val}(in_n)) & \text{if } v \text{ is an } n\text{-ary inner node with operator } \text{op} \text{ and} \\ & \text{with input nodes } in_1 \text{ to } in_n, \text{ and } f = I(\text{op}). \end{cases}$$

The valuation of ADT is defined as the value of its root node $\text{val}(g)$.

Example 6. The algorithm above together with the interpretation in the previous example yield the probability bottom-up traversal semantics, denoted by v^{Pr} .

General Assumptions

While the set of operators for probabilistic ADT analysis can be easily made more general (and time-consuming), see [18], there are the following limits with respect to this type of analysis.

Standard bottom-up traversal algorithms are efficient and correct only on simpler structures than the attack-defense trees of [26] (for more detail, see [33]). In particular, they require a *static interpretation*, i.e. it is decided in one shot which basic events will be tried and which not, see e.g. [39, 31, 21]. Consequently, we exclude RE, SAND and SOR from the PAC-input analysis and restrict this part to trees only, in which every basic events occurs at most once. We include the operator TR if every basic event is triggered by at most one vertex, vertices labelled with TR have no successors and the main tree and the subtrees rooted in vertices with TR are mutually disjoint. In this case, we can ensure that there exists an order satisfying the constraints imposed by TR for each satisfying assignment.

While we present here the bottom-up analysis only under these constraints, in the extended version of this paper ⁸ we discuss how to bound uncertainty even in more complex trees using the *game semantics* of [18].

4.3 PAC-Input Extension of Bottom-Up Analyses

In the following, we devise an algorithmic approach that allows to derive a PAC-aware variant from almost any⁹ bottom-up traversal analysis (according to its previous definition) as long as domain $T \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.¹⁰ To this end, we use the notation $x_i \pm \epsilon_i := [\max(0, x_i - \epsilon_i), x_i + \epsilon_i]$.¹¹

⁸ see 10.5281/zenodo.4095068

⁹ In fact, the approach is independent of the concrete interpretation I chosen, as long as for $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ -interpretation involves solely the operations $+$, $-$, \max , \min and \cdot , or *any combination* thereof.

¹⁰ Further, for instance for the domain of acyclic phase-type distributions, the operations \min , \max and convolutions are allowed.

¹¹ For success probabilities, we set $x_i \pm \epsilon_i := [\max(0, x_i - \epsilon_i), \min(x_i + \epsilon_i, 1)]$

When uncertainty propagates along the nodes during bottom-up traversal analysis, whenever one of the operators $+$, $-$, \cdot over \mathbb{R} is applied during the (standard) analysis, for its *PAC*-aware variant, we additionally need to compute a new uncertainty bound and uncertainty probability for the resulting value based on the imprecision bounds and uncertainty probabilities of its operands. Now we provide bounds on uncertainty propagation for multiplication, addition and inverse of real values.

PAC-Bounds Propagation

Without any assumptions on the distribution of the uncertainty, operations as follows:

Given values $x_1, x_2 \in [0, 1]$ that are (ϵ_i, δ_i) -*PAC*, the uncertainty of

- $1 - x_i$ can be bound by $\epsilon = \epsilon_i$.
- $x_1 \cdot x_2$ can be bound by $\epsilon = x_1 \cdot \epsilon_2 + x_2 \cdot \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$.
- $x_1 + x_2 - x_1 \cdot x_2$ can be bound by $\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + x_1 \cdot \epsilon_2 + x_2 \cdot \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$
- $\max(x_1, x_2)$ can be bound by $\epsilon = \max(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2) + |x_1 - x_2|$
- $\min(x_1, x_2)$ can be bound by $\epsilon = \max(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2) + |x_1 - x_2|$

Independent of the operation, the uncertainty probability δ is (at most) $1 - (1 - \delta_1) \cdot (1 - \delta_2)$ if all x_i are independent, and otherwise (at most) $\delta_1 + \delta_2$.

In summary, the result of each of the given operations is (ϵ, δ) -*PAC*. Furthermore, each constant $c \in \mathbb{R}$ is $(0,0)$ -*PAC*.

Example 7 (PAC-Bounds Computation for Probabilities)

Let ADT be an attack-defense tree with set V of nodes, let val_{BE} be a *PAC* probability valuation for basic events, i.e. for every basic event $\text{be} \in \text{BE}$, it holds $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}(\text{be})$ is $(\epsilon_{\text{be}}, \delta_{\text{be}})$ -*PAC* for some $\epsilon_{\text{be}} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $\delta_{\text{be}} \in [0, 1]$. The uncertainty for $v \in V$ is computed as follows:

1. $v \in \text{BE}$ and v is not triggerable: return $(\epsilon_{\text{be}}, \delta_{\text{be}})$.
2. $v \in \text{BE}$ and v is triggered by v' : recursively compute $(\epsilon_{v'}, \delta_{v'})$. Use rule for multiplication, return $\epsilon = \text{val}(v) \cdot \epsilon_{v'} + \text{val}(v^*) \cdot \epsilon_v + \epsilon_v \cdot \epsilon_{v'}$ and $\delta = \delta_v \cdot \delta_{v'}$.
3. $t(v) = \text{AND}$ and in_1, in_2 are its inputs: recursively compute $(\epsilon_{\text{in}_1}, \delta_{\text{in}_1})$ and $(\epsilon_{\text{in}_2}, \delta_{\text{in}_2})$. Use rule for multiplication, i.e. return $\epsilon = \text{val}(\text{in}_1) \cdot \epsilon_{\text{in}_2} + \text{val}(\text{in}_2) \cdot \epsilon_{\text{in}_1} + \epsilon_{\text{in}_1} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{in}_2}$ and $\delta = \delta_{\text{in}_1} \cdot \delta_{\text{in}_2}$.
4. $t(v) = \text{OR}$ and in_1, in_2 are its inputs: recursively compute $(\epsilon_{\text{in}_1}, \delta_{\text{in}_1})$ and $(\epsilon_{\text{in}_2}, \delta_{\text{in}_2})$. Use rule, i.e. return $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\text{in}_1} + \epsilon_{\text{in}_2} + \text{val}(\text{in}_1) \cdot \epsilon_{\text{in}_2} + \text{val}(\text{in}_2) \cdot \epsilon_{\text{in}_1} + \epsilon_{\text{in}_1} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{in}_2}$ and $\delta = \delta_{\text{in}_1} \cdot \delta_{\text{in}_2}$.
5. $t(v) = \text{NOT}$ and in is its input: recursively compute $(\epsilon_{\text{in}}, \delta_{\text{in}})$ Use rule, i.e. return $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\text{in}}$ and $\delta = \delta_{\text{in}}$.

Theorem 1 (Correctness of PAC Analysis).

Let $\text{ADT} = (V, E, t, \text{Dist}, \text{TEdge}, \text{REdge})$ be an attack-defense tree and let val_{BE} be a *PAC* valuation for basic events, i.e. for every basic event $\text{be} \in \text{BE}$, it holds $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}(\text{be})$ is $(\epsilon_{\text{be}}, \delta_{\text{be}})$ -*PAC* for some $\epsilon_{\text{be}} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $\delta_{\text{be}} \in [0, 1]$. Let $(\epsilon_{\text{Att}}, \delta_{\text{Att}})$ be the error and the probability computed for the goal *Att*. For any valuation $\text{val}^*[\text{BE}]$ such that $\text{val}^*[\text{BE}](\text{be}) \in \text{val}_{\text{BE}}(\text{be}) \pm \epsilon_{\text{be}}$, it holds $\text{val}^*(\text{Att}) \in \text{val}(\text{Att}) \pm \epsilon$.

Proof Sketch. The theorem can be proven by induction on the size of the tree. For non-triggerable basic events, the claim of the theorem holds by assumption. For addition (which we need in the case of **OR**), the uncertainty is just the sum of the individual uncertainties. Uncertainty is unchanged for the inverse element (in the case of **NOT**) and the identity function (in the case of **TR**). For multiplication (**AND** and triggerable basic events), we center the interval around $x_1 \cdot x_2$ by using only upper bound of the uncertainty. We have $(x_1 \pm \epsilon_1) \cdot (x_2 \pm \epsilon_2) = x_1 \cdot x_2 \pm \epsilon_1 \cdot x_2 \pm x_1 \cdot \epsilon_2 \pm \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$. While we can bound the error from above clearly to $\epsilon_1 \cdot x_2 + x_1 \cdot \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$, the respective term $\epsilon_1 \cdot x_2 - x_1 \cdot \epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$ for a bound from below is not correct. Hence, we slightly over-estimate the true error from below to keep a centered interval under any circumstances, but the values are always within the specified bound.

5 Experimental Results

In this section, we show how to analyze our running example using the different exports and analyses **QuADTool** offers and discuss the performance of **QuADTool** on a collection of benchmarks. Both the tool and the benchmarks are available at <https://www7.in.tum.de/~kraemerj/upload/index.php>.

5.1 Running Example

To show the above mentioned features of **QuADTool** and possibilities gained through the support of multiple model-checkers, we use our small running example in Figure 1. It represents an attack to gain access to a computer system. Possible attacks comprise access to a users phone and the corresponding pin to use a smart login system. Another option is to simply wait for the victim to forget logging out of the system. Additionally, one might either find a post-it with the login data or blackmail the user to reveal them. And lastly, the attacker may use the same train as the target and watch them entering their credentials.

5.2 Format Comparison

To demonstrate the restriction of each conversion, we shortly discuss each format. A complete overview can be found in Table 1.

- The export to the **XML**-format is feasible for this model as it is a strict tree-structure with only one root. If there were countermeasure-actions like "change password", they could be included as well. However, additionally including timed events like "wait for server downtime" is not possible.
- Our export to **MODEST** has problems with the above model, as it only consists of player-events. The tool does not efficiently handle this kind of non-determinism in exact model checking and does not support this kind of non-determinism in statistical model checking [7, 23]. To make the model suitable for **MODEST**, one could abstract from player actions using timed basic events. Besides this point, it could be a good choice for models of this structure.
- As the model only contains events triggered by a single player **UPPAAL** is a very good fit for this model.

- Lastly, **PRISM** is the best fit for models that strongly rely on the game characteristics of an ADD. Our case study can be translated to this format as it does not include too many nodes and no reset nodes. Since we explicitly build the whole game, this export is very inefficient and only supports small trees. We recommend it only for small trees with not more than 20 vertices.

Figure 3: Execution times for conversion of dot-files to the other formats. PRISM points missing after size 17 as they reached the timeout of 3 seconds.

5.3 Performance

For performance measurements, we automatically generated models under the above constraints to be able to export in every format possible. Additionally, we only use **AND** and **OR** to avoid deviations with sequential operators as described above. Runtime experiments were executed 50 times reported using the mean (\pm sd), if conversion took more than 3 seconds per iteration the value is considered as not available. The experiments were carried out on a computer with Intel@Core™i7 processor and 16 GB RAM. Figure 3 shows the timeframe needed to convert a model of given size. It is worth noting, that the time includes the loading of the required classes, therefore a certain intercept may exist.

The experiments with the model checkers were conducted with a time frame of 15 minutes per execution and a maximum size between 1100 and 1200 nodes depending on the randomly generated models available, these were only executed five times. Since our tool is limited to about 20 nodes in prism and models of this size caused an stack-overflow error in modest, using mcsta, too, we only conducted these on UPPAAL and ADTool. Fig. 4 shows the runtime for checking the success-probability in both tools. Data suggests that the execution time may depend more

Figure 4: Model checking times for success-probability on the model checkers AD-Tool and UPPAAL-SMC.

Figure 5: Model checking times PAC vs. non-PAC models.

Table 1: Different Approaches to Attack Defense Tree Analysis Support Different Analysis Approaches.

	AND	OR	SAND	TR	RE	NOT	NAT	COST	2-player	time	cost
modeling with QuADTool	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
translation to											
Modest	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	(✓)	✓	✓
UPPAAL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	(✓)	(✓)	×
PRISM	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓
XML for ADTool	✓	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	×	✓	✓	✓
analysis on tree											
probabilities	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	✓	×	×
delay	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	×
cost	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×	✓
PAC	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	✓	✓	✓
dedicated game analysis											
probabilities exact	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓

on the model composition than on the actual size. The reported maximum node-count may be used as a rule of thumb for which system to use. Since all of the model-checkers have different main focuses, the aim was to see if they can handle the models at all.

Format	Conversiontime 11 nodes (ms)	Nodes (conversion)	Nodes (handling)	Benefits
PRISM	175 (± 27)	~20	~20	2-Player games
MODEST	127 (± 10)	>1100	~20	timed events, all operators
UPPAAL	167 (± 12)	>1100	>1100	large models, player driven
XML	173 (± 7)	>1100	>1100	tree structure

Table 2: Performance measures for the supported formats. The maximum nodes may depend on the complexity of the model.

Our experiments show that exports to the model checkers UPPAAL and MODEST and to the XML format are feasible, even for models with around 150 vertices since we do not generate the complete state-space. The use cases mentioned in the introduction usually have significantly smaller models. However, for PRISM, generating the explicit state space of the stochastic turn-based game is too time-consuming for models with more than 20 vertices ((see Figure 3), which is a restriction in practice. In Figure 4, we show the different verification times of our generated models (ADTool vs. UPPAAL). Verification using the ADTool is faster than using UPPAAL. Nevertheless, UPPAAL model checking is useful for more complex objectives. For PAC vs. non-PAC analysis, the results differ roughly by factor 10 in running time. However, none of the approaches takes more than a few

seconds (see Figure 5) even for attack-defense trees with more than 1000 vertices. These results are summarized in Table 2.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

We have presented QuADTool, a tool to model feature-rich attack-defense trees and to translate them to various model checkers for detailed analysis. We also provided a simple, but effective way to bound the uncertainty in quantitative attack tree analysis, using probably approximately correct inputs *and* outputs. Our experiments show that bounding the uncertainty does not tremendously influence the runtime, that modeling with PAC inputs is easy in the tool, and that the PAC requirements can often be satisfied. Finally, we also present ATBEST, the AT BEnchmark SuiTe.

Future Work. There are several ways to be explored to further improve the scalability of the analyses. Firstly, to support larger models and models with heterogeneous subtrees (for instance, one subtree only consisting of **AND** and **OR** and one player, another one requiring full-fledged timed analysis and a third one games), compositional verification techniques could be designed and exploited.

Secondly, both the semantics in terms of stochastic timed automata as well as stochastic turn-based games suffer from a drastic blow-up, especially since all sequences of events need to be taken into account. One could employ partial-order reduction techniques during the conversion to model checkers in order to reduce the model size.

Finally, the support for modeling could also be improved, for instance, by importing log files of attacks and applying existing approaches to AT learning, thus automatically producing AT models from previous experience.

Thanks. We want to thank everyone who has contributed case studies to our benchmark collection ATBEST so far.

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A More Static Quantitative Attack Defense Tree Analysis

The following section recalls definitions from [31] and adapts them to our attack-defense tree setting. *We only allow trees here (no DAGs).* In contrast to [31], we allow TR as a restricted variant of SAND¹² and use NOT rather than player swapping to focus on the player *controlling* an event rather than whether an event is *useful* or *hindering* for an attack. Additionally, we assume that every basic event can only occur once in the tree. Thus, we restrict the multiset semantics of [39, 31] to a powerset semantics.

Let X be a set and let $X_1, X_2 \subseteq 2^X$, i.e. X_1 and X_2 are sets of sets with elements in X . We define $X_1 \otimes X_2 := \bigcup_{(x_1, x_2) \in X_1 \times X_2} \{x_1 \cup x_2\}$. To restrict a set of basic events X to the basic events occurring in the subtree rooted in a vertex \mathbf{v} , we write $X|_{\mathbf{v}}$.

Definition 2 (Powerset Attack-Defense Trees). *We consider the operators AND, OR, TR and NOT and let all basic events be in $\text{BA} \dot{\cup} \text{BD}$. We define a powerset interpretation I with $\mathsf{T} = 2^{2^{\text{BE}}} \times 2^{2^{\text{BE}}}$.*

- $\mathsf{I}(\mathbf{v})((X_{11}, X_{12}), (X_{21}, X_{22})) = (X_{11} \otimes X_{21}, X_{21} \cup X_{22} \cup (X_{21} \otimes X_{22})) \cup (X_{12} \otimes X_{21}) \cup (X_{11} \otimes X_{22})$ if \mathbf{v} is a triggerable basic event or $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{AND}$
- $\mathsf{I}(\mathbf{v})((X_{11}, X_{12}), (X_{21}, X_{22})) = ((X_{11} \cup X_{21} \cup (X_{11} \otimes X_{21}) \cup (X_{12} \otimes X_{21}) \cup (X_{11} \otimes X_{22})), (X_{12} \otimes X_{22}))$ for $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{OR}$
- $\mathsf{I}(\text{NOT})((X_1, X_2)) = (X_2, X_1)$
- $\mathsf{I}(\text{TR}) = \text{Id}$

We denote the powerset bottom-up traversal semantics by val^P .

The powerset bottom-up traversal semantics computes two sets of sets. In the first component, we collect all satisfying assignments, in the second one all unsatisfying assignments. Please note that we only denote events, which need to be set to true. All events not contained, need to be set to false.

To compute successful and unsuccessful attacks at once, we need to set $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}^P(\text{be}) := (\{\{\text{be}\}\}, \{\emptyset\})$. For the powerset bottom-up traversal semantics, we implicitly assume this valuation for basic events in the following.

Definition 3 (Boolean Attack-Defense Trees). *We consider the operators AND, OR, TR and NOT and let all basic events be in $\text{BA} \dot{\cup} \text{BD}$. We define a Boolean interpretation I with $\mathsf{T} = \{\text{tt}, \text{ff}\}$*

- $\mathsf{I}(\mathbf{v})(x_1, x_2) = \wedge$, if \mathbf{v} is a triggerable basic event or $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{AND}$
- $\mathsf{I}(\mathbf{v}) = \vee$ for $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{OR}$
- $\mathsf{I}(\text{NOT}) = \neg$
- $\mathsf{I}(\text{TR}) = \text{Id}$

We denote the Boolean bottom-up traversal semantics by val^B .

Let $X \subseteq \text{BE}$. In the following, we denote by $\text{val}_{\text{BE}, X}^B$ the Boolean valuation such that $\text{val}_{\text{BE}, X}^B(\text{be}) = \text{tt}$ if $\text{be} \in X$ and false, otherwise.

¹² We use SAND to represent a timed order and TR to represent a logic order.

Theorem 2 (Powerset and Boolean Attack-Defense Trees). Let $\text{ADT} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathbf{t}, \text{Dist}, \text{TEdge}, \text{REdge})$ be an attack-defense tree and let $\text{val}^P(\mathbf{v}) = (X_1, X_2)$.

1. $x_1 \in X_1$ iff $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{tt}$ w.r.t. $\text{val}_{\text{BE},x_1}^B$
2. $x_2 \in X_2$ iff $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{tt}$ w.r.t. $\text{val}_{\text{BE},x_2}^B$

Proof. Let $\text{ADT} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathbf{t}, \text{Dist}, \text{TEdge}, \text{REdge})$ be an attack-defense tree. We proof both claims simultaneously by induction on the structure of the attack-defense tree.

- \mathbf{v} is a non-triggerable basic event. By definition $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{tt}$ iff $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{tt}$. Since $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}^P(\mathbf{v}) = (\{\{\mathbf{v}\}\}, \{\emptyset\})$, the claims holds true.
- *Induction Hypothesis:* For all subtrees of \mathbf{v} rooted in \mathbf{v}^* holds:
 1. $x_1 \in X_1$ iff $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}^*) = \text{tt}$ w.r.t. $\text{val}_{\text{BE},x_1}^B$
 2. $x_2 \in X_2$ iff $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}^*) = \text{tt}$ w.r.t. $\text{val}_{\text{BE},x_2}^B$
- $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{TR}$: The claim holds by induction hypothesis and the definitions of val^P and val^B (identity function for vertices labelled by TR).
- $\mathbf{v} \in \text{BE}$ and triggered by $\mathbf{v}^* \in \mathcal{V}$. Let $\text{val}^P(\mathbf{v}^*) = (X_1^*, X_2^*)$. We have $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}^P(\mathbf{v}) = (\{\{\mathbf{v}\}\}, \{\emptyset\})$ and $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}^*) \wedge \text{val}^B(\mathbf{v})$. Thus, every satisfying assignment of the subtree rooted in \mathbf{v}^* extended by \mathbf{v} set to true is a satisfying assignment of \mathbf{v} . We apply the induction hypothesis to the subtree rooted in \mathbf{v}^* . Hence, by definition of \otimes and the induction hypothesis, Claim (1) holds true. Additionally, $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{ff}$ if \mathbf{v} is set to false (i.e. $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{ff}$) or $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}^*) = \text{ff}$. Hence, by induction hypothesis and the definition of val^P for triggerable basic events, Claim (2) holds, too.
- $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{AND}$: Analogously to the proof for triggerable basic events. However, the induction hypothesis needs to be used on both subtrees.
- $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{OR}$: Analogously to the proof for triggerable basic events. However, the induction hypothesis needs to be used for both subtrees and the proofs of the two claims need to be swapped.
- $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{NOT}$: Let \mathbf{v}^* be the input of \mathbf{v} and let $\text{val}^P(\mathbf{v}^*) = (X_1, X_2)$. Since $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}) = \text{tt}$ iff $\text{val}^B(\mathbf{v}^*) = \text{ff}$ by definition and each satisfying assignment of \mathbf{v}^* is an unsatisfying assignment of \mathbf{v} by definition, the claim follows from the induction hypothesis.

We have proven Theorem 2 by induction.

Let $\text{ADT} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathbf{t}, \text{Dist}, \text{TEdge}, \text{REdge})$ be an attack-defense tree. We say that a valuation $\text{val}_{\text{BE}} : \text{BE} \rightarrow \{\text{tt}, \text{ff}\}$ is a *successful attack* if $\mathbf{v}(\text{Att}) = \text{tt}$, and *unsuccessful attack* otherwise¹³. We say a successful attack is *minimal* if there does not exist an basic event be such that $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}(\text{be}) = \text{tt}$ and the modified valuation val^* where

To account for NOT, we need to compute simultaneously the minimal/maximal cost/delay for failing, too.

¹³ Dually, this can be done for defenses by assigning the goal **Att** to the defender. Since we do not use player swapping as in [31], there are no changes necessary to this or the following semantics to apply them to defenses. However, the valuation of the basic events might need to be modified (for instance, excluding costs of the attacker when computing costs of successful defenses). In the following, we only talk about attacks and do not explicitly state that our results are dually correct for defenses.

Definition 4 (Delay Attack-Defense Trees). We consider the operators AND, OR, TR and NOT and let all basic events be in $BA \dot{\cup} BD$. We define a probabilistic interpretation l with $T = \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.

- $l(v)((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) = (\max(x_1, y_1), \min(x_2, y_2))$ (minimal delay) and $(\max(x_1, y_1), \max(x_2, y_2))$ (maximal delay), if v is a triggerable basic event or if $t(v) = \text{AND}$.
- $l(v)((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) = (\min(x_1, y_1), \max(x_2, y_2))$ for the minimal delay and $l(v)((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) = (\max(x_1, y_1), \max(x_2, y_2))$ for the maximal delay (if events cannot fail) if $t(v) = \text{OR}$
- $l(\text{NOT})(x_1, x_2) = (x_2, x_1)$
- $l(\text{TR}) = \text{ld}$

We denote the minimal delay bottom-up traversal semantics by $v^{\text{Delay, min}}$ and the maximal cost bottom-up traversal semantics by $v^{\text{Delay, max}}$

Definition 5 (Cost Attack-Defense Trees). We consider the operators AND, OR, TR and NOT and let all basic events be in $BA \dot{\cup} BD$. We define a probabilistic interpretation l with $T = \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$.

- $l(v)((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) = (x_1 + y_1, \min(x_2, y_2))$ (minimal delay) and $(x_1 + y_1, \max(x_2, y_2))$ (maximal delay), if v is a triggerable basic event or if $t(v) = \text{AND}$
- $l(v)((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) = (\min(x_1, y_1), x_2 + y_2)$ for the minimal cost and $l(v)((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) = (\max(x_1, y_1), x_2 + y_2)$ for the maximal cost (if events cannot fail) if $t(v) = \text{OR}$
- $l(\text{NOT})(x_1, x_2) = (x_2, x_1)$
- $l(\text{TR}) = \text{ld}$

We denote the minimal cost bottom-up traversal semantics by $v^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}$ and the maximal cost bottom-up traversal semantics by $v^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{max}}$

We use $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E}[\text{BE}](\text{be}) = (\text{Cost}_E, 0)$ and $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}}[\text{BE}](\text{be}) = (\text{Delay}, 0)$. Cost and delays just occur if basic events are successfully attempted in an attack.

Theorem 3 (Correctness w.r.t. Boolean Semantics). Let $\text{ADT} = (V, E, t, \text{Dist}, \text{TEdge}, \text{REdge})$ be an attack-defense tree and val_{BE} be a successful attack, let $v \in V$ and $\text{val}^P(v) = (X_1, X_2)$. It holds:

1. $\text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v) = \sum_{x_1 \in X_1} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_1|_v} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_1} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$
 $= 1 - \sum_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_2|_v} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be}).$
2. $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}(v) = (\min_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}), \min_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be})).$
3. $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{max}}(v) = (\max_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}), \max_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be})).$
4. $\text{val}^{\text{Delay, min}}(v) = (\min_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Delay}(\text{be}), \min_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Delay}(\text{be})).$
5. $\text{val}^{\text{Delay, max}}(v) = (\max_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Delay}(\text{be}), \max_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Delay}(\text{be})).$

Proof. We prove all claims by an induction on the tree structure.

- v is a non-triggerable basic event. For each of the five functions, the value assigned to the basic event is returned. since $(X_1|_v, X_2|_v) = (\{\{\text{be}\}\}, \{\emptyset\})$, the claims hold by definition.
- *Induction Hypothesis:* For subtrees rooted in a v^* of v , it holds:
 - $\text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v^*) = \sum_{x_1 \in X_1} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_1} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$
 $= 1 - \sum_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_2|_v} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be}).$
 - $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}(v^*) = (\min_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}), \min_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be})).$
 - $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{max}}(v^*) = (\max_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}), \max_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be})).$
 - $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{min}}(v^*) = (\min_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Delay}(\text{be}), \min_{x_2|_v \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2|_v} \text{Delay}(\text{be})).$
 - $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{max}}(v^*) = (\max_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Delay}(\text{be}), \max_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Delay}(\text{be})).$
- $t(v) = \text{TR}$: The claims follow by definition of val^{Pr} , $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}$, $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{max}}$, $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{min}}$ and $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{max}}$ and the induction hypothesis (since TR maps to the identity function in all cases).
- $t(v) = \text{NOT}$: Let v^* be the input of vertex. The claims for $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}$, $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{max}}$, $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{min}}$ and $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{max}}$ follow by their definition and the induction hypothesis (since NOT just swaps the components in these cases). For val^{Pr} , it holds $\text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v) = 1 - \text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v^*)$. By induction hypothesis, we have
 - $1 - \text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v^*) = 1 - \sum_{x_1 \in X_1|_{v^*}} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_1} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$. By the definition of val^{Pr} for NOT, this is equivalent to $1 - \sum_{x_2 \in X_2|_{v^*}} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_2} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_2|_v} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$.
 - $1 - \text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v^*) = 1 - (1 - \sum_{x_2 \in X_2|_{v^*}} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_2} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_2} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be}))$. By definition of val^{Pr} for NOT, this is equivalent to $\sum_{x_1 \in X_1} 1 - \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_1} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) = \sum_{x_1 \in X_1} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Pr}(\text{be})$
- v is a triggerable basic event and triggered by v^* . Let $(X_1, X_2) = \text{val}^P(v)$. We apply the induction hypothesis to v^* .
 - Let $(x, y) = \text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}(v^*)$. $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{min}}(v) = (x + \text{Cost}_E(v), \min(y, \text{Cost}_E(v))) = (\min_{x_1 \in X_1|_{v^*}} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}) + \text{Cost}_E(v), \min(y, \text{Cost}_E(v)))$
 $= (\min_{x_1 \in X_1} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}), \min_{x_2 \in X_2} \sum_{\text{be} \in x_2} \text{Cost}_E(\text{be}))$ by the definition of val^P for triggerable basic events (in the first component, we combine add the vertex to all satisfying assignments of the input, in the second component, we have a union of all unsatisfying assignments, so the minimal element can be computed this way).
 - Analogously, we can prove the claims for $\text{val}^{\text{Cost}_E, \text{max}}$, $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{min}}$ and $\text{val}^{\text{Delay}, \text{max}}$
 - $\text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v) = \text{val}^{\text{Pr}}(v^*) \cdot \text{Pr}(v)$. By induction hypothesis, this is equivalent to $(\sum_{x_1 \in X_1|_{v^*}} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_1} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})) \cdot \text{Pr}(v) = \sum_{x_1 \in X_1} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_1} \text{Pr}(\text{be})$.

$\prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_1} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$. On the other hand,
 $1 - \sum_{x_2 \in X_2} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_2} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_2} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$

is equivalent to $1 - (k \cdot (1 - \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v})) + k \cdot \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) + (1 - k) \cdot (1 - \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v})))$ where
 $k = \sum_{x_2 \in X_2 \setminus \mathbf{v}^*} \prod_{\text{be} \in x_2} \text{Pr}(\text{be}) \cdot \prod_{\text{be} \in \text{BE} \setminus x_2} 1 - \text{Pr}(\text{be})$ by definition of val^P
for triggerable basic events. We have $1 - (k - k \cdot \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) + k \cdot \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) + 1 - k - \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) + k \cdot \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v})) = 1 - (1 - \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) + k \cdot \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v})) = \text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) \cdot (1 - k)$. By
induction hypothesis, this is equivalent to $\text{Pr}(\mathbf{v}) \cdot \text{val}^{\mathbb{P}}(\mathbf{v}^*)$, which matches
the definition of $\text{val}^{\mathbb{P}}$ for triggerable basic events.

- $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{AND}$: Analogously to the proof for triggerable basic events. However, the induction hypothesis needs to be used on both subtrees.
- $\mathbf{t}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{OR}$: Analogously to the proof for triggerable basic events. However, the induction hypothesis needs to be used for both subtrees and the proofs of the two claims need to be swapped.

Since computing PAC values is independent of the exact attack-defense tree interpretation, but depends on the operators used on \mathbb{T} , the operators defined suffice to also augment cost and delay analyses with PAC values.

Recap of Theorem 4. Let $\text{ADT} = (\mathbb{V}, \mathbb{E}, \mathbf{t}, \text{Dist}, \mathbb{T}\text{Edge}, \mathbb{R}\text{Edge})$ be an attack-defense tree and let val_{BE} be a PAC valuation for basic events, i.e. for every basic event $\text{be} \in \text{BE}$, it holds $\text{val}_{\text{BE}}(\text{be})$ is $(\epsilon_{\text{be}}, \delta_{\text{be}})$ -PAC for some $\epsilon_{\text{be}} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $\delta_{\text{be}} \in [0, 1]$. Let $(\epsilon_{\text{Att}}, \delta_{\text{Att}})$ be the error and the probability computed for the goal **Att**. For any valuation $\text{val}^*[\text{BE}]$ such that $\text{val}^*[\text{BE}](\text{be}) \in \text{val}_{\text{BE}}(\text{be}) \pm \epsilon_{\text{be}}$, it holds $\text{val}^*(\text{Att}) \in \text{val}(\text{Att}) \pm \epsilon$.

Proof (of Theorem 1). Instead of proving the claim directly, we show that for any two PAC values $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ (with ϵ_x, δ_x and ϵ_y, δ_y), respectively), it holds: Let $x^* \in x \pm \epsilon_x$ and $y^* \in y \pm \epsilon_y$ ¹⁴, then

1. $(1 - x^*) \in (1 - x) \pm \epsilon$: x^* is at most ϵ_x away from x , i.e. the values range from $(1 - (x + \epsilon_x)) = (1 - x) - \epsilon_x$ to $(1 - (x - \epsilon_x)) = (1 - x) + \epsilon_x$.
2. $x^* \cdot y^* \in (x \cdot y) \pm x \cdot \epsilon_y + y \cdot \epsilon_x + \epsilon_x \cdot \epsilon_y$: This claim follows by $(x \pm \epsilon_x) \cdot (y \pm \epsilon_y) = y \cdot x \pm \epsilon_x \cdot y \pm y \cdot \epsilon_x \pm \epsilon_x \cdot \epsilon_y$ ¹⁵.
3. $x^* + y^* \in x + y \pm (\epsilon_x + \epsilon_y)$: The claim holds since $(x + \epsilon_x) + (y + \epsilon_y) = x + y + (\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y)$ and $(x - \epsilon_x) + (y - \epsilon_y) = x + y - (\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y)$.
4. $x^* + y^* - x^* \cdot y^* \in (x + y - x \cdot y) \pm \epsilon_x + \epsilon_y + x \cdot \epsilon_y + y \cdot \epsilon_x + \epsilon_x \cdot \epsilon_y$: This case is a combination case 2 and case 3. of

¹⁴ We cut off operations at 0 for all quantitative domains and at 1 for success probabilities for all computations with ϵ , i.e. if $x - \epsilon_x < 0$, we replace the actual result with 0. If $x + \epsilon_x > 1$ (and we compute success probabilities), we replace the actual result by 1. We do not explicitly mention this in the following.

¹⁵ While we can bound the error from above clearly to $\epsilon_1 \cdot x_2 + x_2 \cdot \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$, the respective term $\epsilon_1 \cdot x_2 - x_2 \cdot \epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1 \cdot \epsilon_2$ for a bound from below is not correct. Nevertheless, we slightly over-estimate the true error from below to keep a centered interval under any circumstances and the claim still holds.

5. $\max(x^*, y^*) \in \max(x, y) \pm \max(\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y) + |x - y|$: $\max(x + \epsilon_x, y + \epsilon_y)$ and $\max(x - \epsilon_x, y - \epsilon_y)$ are the maximal and minimal values $\max(x^*, y^*)$ can obtain. So, the biggest error from the maximal value is given by the biggest error of the individual and the distance between the two centers.¹⁶
6. $\min(x^*, y^*) \in \min(x, y) \pm \max(\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y) + |x - y|$: Analogously to case 5.

The result of Theorem 1 then follows from a straightforward induction on the structure of the tree.

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B Bounding Uncertainty for More Complex Attack-Defense Trees

C Formal Definition to Attack-Defense Trees

Formally, we define the set of all operators $\mathcal{O} = \{\text{AND, OR, NOT, NAT, COST, RE, TR, SAND, SOR}\}$.

Definition 6 (Definition 1 of [26], leaving out IF). An attack-defense tree is a tuple $\text{ADT} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathfrak{t}, \text{Dist}, \text{TEdge}, \text{REdge})$ where

- $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ is a directed acyclic graph, with a designated goal sink vertex Att for the attacker. The source vertices $\text{BE} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ are called basic events (BE) ($\text{BE} = \text{BE}_A \dot{\cup} \text{BE}_D \dot{\cup} \text{BE}_T$). All other vertices, $\text{CE} := \mathcal{V} \setminus \text{BE}$, are called gates; direct predecessors w.r.t. $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ of each gate are called its inputs. T
- $\mathfrak{t}: \text{CE} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$ is the type function assigning an operator to each gate.
- $\text{Dist}: \text{BE}_T \rightarrow \text{CDFs}$ assigns to each time-driven basic event a cumulative distribution function over its positive delay,
- $\text{TEdge} \subseteq \{\mathfrak{v} \in \text{CE} \mid \mathfrak{t}(\mathfrak{v}) = \text{TR}\} \times \text{BE}$ are trigger edges from TR gates to BE;
- $\text{REdge} \subseteq \{\mathfrak{v} \in \text{CE} \mid \mathfrak{t}(\mathfrak{v}) = \text{RE}\} \times \text{BE}$ are reset edges from RE gates to BE;
- We additionally require . . .
 - that gates of type AND, OR, SAND, SOR have at least two inputs and that other gates have exactly one input.
 - each vertex $\mathfrak{v} \in \mathcal{V}$ labeled by COST to be equipped with a comparison operator $\text{op}(\mathfrak{v}) \in \{\leq, <, \geq, >, =, \neq\}$ and a bound $\mathcal{B}(\mathfrak{v}) \in \mathbb{R}$, relating to the costs accumulated so far.

To analyze the success probability of attacks, their costs and their timing, we equip basic events with success probabilities, costs, delays and distributions as follows:

- $\text{Pr}: \text{BE} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ assigns to each basic event the probability of its *successful execution*,
- Let CVars be a finite set of cost variables. Then $\text{Cost}_E: \text{BE} \times \text{CVars} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ specifies for every pair of basic event and cost variable the cost the execution of the basic event will cause.

¹⁶ Using assumptions on the distribution of the error, more precise estimates are possible.

- Delay: $BE \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ specifies for every basic event its time delay before execution.
- Dist: $BE_T \rightarrow \mathcal{D}$ specifies for every time-driven basic event its distribution function.

Please note the following differences to other attack-defense tree definitions:

- vertices (except basic events and the goal) are not assigned players
- trigger and reset edges are not part of set of edges E , we consider only (V, E) to be acyclic (together with trigger edges and reset edges, this does not need to be the case)

Essentially, attack-defense trees (ADT) in our context are limited cyclic and not necessarily connected directed graphs, which are labeled with *events*.¹⁷ $BE := BE_A \dot{\cup} BE_D \dot{\cup} BE_T$, i.e., every basic event either belongs to the **A**ttacker or to the **D**efender or is Time-driven. All other vertices are labeled with operators and called *composed events*.

We here use an extension of attack trees proposed in [26], since its expressiveness overarches current attack tree approaches. It does not only feature logic operators such as **AND**, **OR**, **NOT**, **NAT** and sequential versions **SAND**, **SOR**, but also two operators dedicated to manipulate the availability of basic events over time (**TR** and **RE**) as well as an operator which allows specifying bounds on resources directly on the tree (**COST**).

¹⁷ We call them attack defense *trees* since we can transform trees into directed acyclic graphs in a preprocessing step by joining multiple copies of the same events.